

Guidelines and Style for IRRN Contributors

To improve communication and to speed the editorial process the editors of the International Rice Research Newsletter (IRRN) request that contributors use the following guidelines and style:

Style

- Use the metric system in all papers. Avoid national units of measure (such as cavans, rai, etc)
- Express all yields in tons per hectare (t/ha) or, with small-scale studies, in grams per pot (g/pot) or grams per row (g/row).
- Define in footnotes or legends any abbreviations or symbols used in a figure or table.
- Place the name or denotation of compounds or chemicals near the unit of measure. For example 60 kg N/ha: not 60 kg/ha N.
- The US dollar is the standard monetary unit for the *IRRN*. Data in other currencies should be converted to US\$.
- Abbreviate names of standard units of measure when they follow a number. For example 20 kg/ha
- When using abbreviation other than for units of measure spell out the full name the first time of reference, with abbreviation in parenthesis, then use the abbreviation throughout the remaining text. For example: The efficiency of nitrogen (N) use was tested. Three levels of N were.... or Biotypes of the brown planthopper (BPH) differ within Asia. We studied the biotypes of BPH in....
- Express time, money, and measurement in numbers, even when the amount is less than 10. For example: 8 years; 3 kg/ha at 2-week intervals; 7%; 4 hours.
- Write out numbers below 10 except in a series containing some numbers 10 or higher and some numbers lower than 10. For example six parts; seven tractors: four varieties. *But* There were 4 plots in India, 8 plots in Thailand, and 12 plots in Indonesia.
- Write out all numbers that start sentences. For example: Sixty insects were added to each cage, Seventy-five percent of the yield increase is attributed to fertilizer use.

Guidelines

- Contributions to the IRRN should generally be based on results of research on rice or on cropping patterns involving rice.
- Appropriate statistical analyses are required for most data.
- Contributions should not exceed two pages of double-spaced, typewritten text. Two figures (graphs, tables, or photos) per contribution are permitted to supplement the text. The editor will return articles that exceed space limitations.
- Results of routine screening of rice cultivars are discouraged. Exceptions will be made only if screening reveals previously unreported information (for example, a new source of genetic resistance to rice pests).
- Announcements of the release of new rice varieties are encouraged.
- Use common — not trade — names for commercial chemicals and, when feasible, equipment.
- Do not include references in IRRN contributions.
- Pest surveys should be quantified with data (% infection, degree of severity, etc.).

Genetic evaluation and utilization

OVERALL PROGRESS

Performance of Indian rice varieties in Afghanistan

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The adaptability of 571 Indian varieties to local conditions was tested 1970-80. First screenings were in observational plots, initial evaluation trials, or IRTP nurseries at Baghlan in the Northern Zone, with a temperate climate, and at Jalalabad in the Eastern Zone, with a subtropical climate.

Entries which matured in time were classified as fine-grained or coarse-grained varieties. Local fine-grained varieties Barah and Pashadi and coarse-grained variety LUK were the checks. Each crop was transplanted in rows 20 cm apart with hills 15 cm apart, 2-3 seedlings/hill. High fertility (120 kg N, 60 kg P₂O₅, and 30 kg K₂O₄/ha) and good management practices were used.

Flowering of most varieties was delayed. Of 571 entries, only 48 (8.14%)

at Baghlan and 94 (16.04%) at Jalalabad matured in time. Fourteen varieties at Baghlan and 21 at Jalalabad performed better than the local checks.

Yields of 4 fine-grained varieties at Baghlan and 12 fine-grained varieties at Jalalabad were more than the yields of the local checks (Table 1). At Baghlan, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 5-9 t/ha to 8.8 t/ha compared to 5-6.4 t/ha for local variety Barah, a yield difference of 18-37%.

At Jalalabad, average yields of fine-grained varieties ranged from 4.1 t/ha to 7 t/ha compared to 2.4-5.2 t/ha for local variety Pashadi, a yield difference of 4-135%.

CR44-11, with quality characters similar to those of Pashadi and almost double its yield potential, was released in 1975 as an improved variety for general cultivation in the Eastern Zone.

The yields of 10 coarse-grained varieties at Baghlan and 9 coarse-grained varieties at Jalalabad were more than the yield of the local check (Table 2). At

Table 1. Yields of promising fine-grained Indian rice varieties at the Agricultural Research Stations at Baghlan and Jalalabad, Afghanistan, 1970-80.

Variety	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Increase over local variety	
		Indian variety	Local variety ^a	t/ha	%
<i>Baghlan</i>					
RP19-23	2	5.9	5.0	0.9	18
IET849	2	7.1	5.0	2.1	43
KC10	4	7.6	5.6	2.0	36
PuSa 33-1 8	2	8.8	6.4	2.4	38
<i>Jalalabad</i>					
RP19-23	3	6.4	4.0	2.4	58
IET849	2	5.7	5.2	0.6	11
CR44-11	18	6.3	3.2	3.2	100
CR113-91	3	4.1	3.9	0.2	4
CR44-35	2	6.8	4.2	2.6	60
ET1522	3	6.9	4.0	2.9	70
Ratna	3	6.7	2.8	3.8	135
KT1526	3	7.0	4.1	2.8	68
KC14	4	5.0	2.4	1.6	108
KC15	5	5.3	2.8	2.5	91
ET2845	2	7.0	3.2	3.8	116
ET3262	2	5.7	3.2	2.4	75

^aBarah at Baghlan and Pashadi at Jalalabad.

Table 2. Yields of promising coarse-grained Indian rice varieties at the Agricultural Research Stations at Baghlan and Jalalabad, 1970-80.

Variety	Trials (no.)	Av yield (t/ha)		Increase over local variety	
		Indian variety	Local variety (LUK)	t/ha	%
<i>Baghlan</i>					
IET400	3	7.9	4.2	3.7	87
CR75-8	3	5.8	4.1	1.7	41
CR10-114	4	7.4	4.0	3.4	83
IET355	12	8.8	3.6	5.1	140
Padma	3	5.2	4.9	0.3	6
CR36-148	4	9.3	3.1	6.2	204
KH7194	3	10.2	3.6	5.7	180
K103-2-32	2	9.1	4.8	4.3	88
K103-2-3	2	7.4	4.8	2.6	53
K78-2	2	6.6	4.8	1.7	36
<i>Jalalabad</i>					
IET400	4	6.4	3.5	2.9	82
CR75-8	6	5.0	2.8	2.3	81
CR10-114	5	6.0	3.4	2.6	77
IET355	6	5.6	3.0	2.6	84
Padma	11	7.0	2.7	4.3	158
CR36-148	4	5.7	3.8	1.9	51
Jaya	2	4.6	3.8	0.8	22
CR44-1	6	5.8	3.2	2.9	80
CR115-76	2	6.1	3.7	2.4	65

Baghlan, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 5.2 t/ha to 10.2 t/ha compared to 3.1-4.9 t/ha for local variety LUK, a yield difference of 6-204%. At Jalalabad, average yields of Indian varieties ranged from 4.6 t/ha to 7 t/ha compared to 2.7-3.8 t/ha for the local variety, a yield difference of 22-158%.

IET355 in the Northern Zone and Padma in the Eastern Zone were released as improved varieties in 1975. KH7194 is being tested on cultivators' fields in the Northern Zone to replace IET355. No variety has been identified to replace Padma in the Eastern Zone.

Varieties with 100- to 110-day durations in India are suitable for introduction in Afghanistan. Yield levels of Indian varieties were generally higher at Baghlan than at Jalalabad, perhaps because of the better environment in the Northern Zone. ■

CR1009, a promising rice cultivar

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CR1009 (IET5897), a promising long-duration rice cultivar evolved at the Central Rice Research Institute, Cuttack, is a cross between Pankaj and

Jagannath. It is semidwarf, with high tillering, medium-compact panicle, and white, short, bold grains.

The performance of CR1009 and of long-duration varieties Co 25, Co 40, and NLR 9672 was tested at PES, Tirurkuppam, during the samba season (August-January) from 1977-78 to 1980-81. CR1009 recorded a mean yield of 4.4 t/ha. Its duration was 151-165 days (Table 1).

CR1009 was also grown in farmers' fields in Thanjavur district during 1981-82 samba (Table 2). ■

Table 2. Performance of CR1009 in farmers' fields, Thanjavur district, India, 1981-82.

Farm size (ha)	Av grain yield (t/ha)
1.4	6.7
3.6	6.4
7.0	5.6

Table 1. Performance of CR1009 in samba season at Tamil Nadu, India.

Rice cultivar	1977-78		1978-79		1979-80		1980-81		Av Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)
	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)	Yield (t/ha)	Duration (days)		
CR1009	5.7	151	4.3	162	4.4	155	3.0	165	4.35	151-165
Co 25	4.5	168	2.8	162	2.8	175	2.3	178	3.10	162-178
Co 40	5.9	162	3.7	150	3.9	165	2.5	178	4.00	150-178
NLR9672	NT	NT	3.7	151	4.1	165	2.1	175	3.30	151-175
<i>F</i> -test	Significant		Not significant		Significant		Not significant			
C.D. (<i>P</i> = 0.05)	1.30		-		0.46		0.65			

New rice varieties for Rajasthan

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Three new rice varieties — Chambal, BK190, and BK79 — were recently named by the University of Udaipur and

released for general cultivation in Rajasthan.

Chambal (IR8/NP130) is a dwarf, photoperiod-insensitive variety that matures in 135-140 days. Early seedling vigor is good and tillering ability is moderate. It has highly synchronized flowering, late leaf senescence, and stiff

straw. Grains are slightly longer than those of IR8 and protein content is higher. Average yield is 7.3 t/ha.

BK190 (R14/IR8) is an intermediate height, photoperiod-insensitive indica variety that matures in 145-155 days. Early seedling vigor is excellent and tillering capacity is good. Very sturdy